

DFT Functionals for Modeling of Polyethylene Chains Cross-linked by Metal Atoms. DLPNO-CCSD(T) Benchmark Calculations.

Martin Blaško¹, Lukáš F. Pašteka², Miroslav Urban*²

¹ *FunGlass, A. Dubček University of Trenčín, Študentská 2, 911 50 Trenčín, Slovakia*

² *Department of Physical and Theoretical Chemistry, Faculty of Natural Sciences, Comenius University in Bratislava, Ilkovičova 6, 84215 Bratislava, Slovakia*

ABSTRACT

DFT functionals for calculations of binding energies (BEs) of the polyethylene (PE) chains cross-linked by selected metal atoms (M) are benchmarked against DLPNO-CCSD(T) and DLPNO-CCSD(T1) data. PEX-M-PEX complexes as compared with plain parallel PEX···PEX chains with X = 3 – 9 carbon atoms are model species characterized by cooperative effect of covalent C-M-C bonds and interchain dispersion interactions. The accuracy of DLPNO-CC methods was assessed by comparison of BEs with the canonical CCSD(T) results for small PE₃-M-PE₃ complexes. Functionals for PEX···PEX and closed-shell PEX-M-PEX complexes (M = Be, Mg, Zn) were benchmarked against DLPNO-CCSD(T) BEs, open-shell complexes (M = Li, Ag, Au) were benchmarked against the DLPNO-CCSD(T1) method with iterative triples. Three dispersion corrections were combined with 25 DFT functionals for calculations of BEs with respect to PEX-M and PEX fragments employing def2-TZVPP and def2-QZVPP basis sets. Accuracy to within 5% for the closed-shell PEX-M-PEX complexes was achieved with five functionals. Less accurate are functionals for the open-shell PEX-M-PEX complexes; only two functionals deviate by less than 15% from DLPNO-CCSD(T1). Particularly problematic were PEX-Li-PEX complexes. Reasonable overall performance across all complexes in terms of the Mean Absolute Percent Error (MAPE) is found for range-separated hybrid functionals ω B97X-D3 and CAM-B3LYP/D3(BJ)-ABC.

Key words: benchmarking DFT, DLPNO-CCSD(T), DLPNO-CCSD(T1), C-M-C bonds, dispersion interactions, polyethylene cross-linking, cross-linking elements Be, Mg, Zn, Li, Ag, Au, new materials.

Miroslav Urban, urban1@uniba.sk tel. +421902219988, ORCID: 0000-0003-0379-6414

Martin Blaško, martin.blasko@tuni.sk ORCID: 0000-0001-5070-7774

Lukáš F. Pašteka, lukas.f.pasteka@uniba.sk ORCID: 0000-0002-0617-0524

INTRODUCTION

Polyethylene (PE) is a material with a considerable spectrum of applications. Modification of its properties like creep behavior, thermal resistance, surface tension, adhesion, electrical conductivity, etc. by cross-linking is well understood and commercially applied process. It is most frequently accomplished by a radical mechanism based on the formation of macroradicals (created by ionizing radiation, peroxide or silane chemistry) and their subsequent recombination with the participation of polymer chains with a separable hydrogen¹. Large spectrum of desired properties of PE based materials leads to different cross-linking methods investigated by both experimentalists and theoreticians²⁻¹².

Effective development of new materials designed for a specific use can be supported, guided, or initiated by computational modelling. Using DFT calculations, we have suggested that cross-linking of the polyethylene (PE) via implemented gold atoms could be a viable alternative to polymer cross-linking by a common radical mechanism^{13,14}. Gold atoms as cross-linking agents can create quite strong interchain bonds and support well organized parallel structures of PE chains, in contrast to the common radical cross-linking. The model for PE – metal cross-linking was based on optimization of structures represented by two oligomer PEX chains bound by one to three Au atoms, PEX-Au_n-PEX ($n = 1 - 3$; X up to 23, represents the number of C atoms in each oligomer). The suggested bonding mechanism is the concerned action of covalent C-Au-C bonds and dispersion interactions between oligomer chains. The idea has emerged from observations that gold atoms can substitute hydrogens in hydrocarbons forming auro-carbons¹⁵ with quite strong C-Au bonds¹⁶⁻²⁵. Detailed analysis of the bonding mechanism and binding energies (BEs) of Au atoms with PE and possible experimental identification of Au-C bonds via the vibrational spectroscopy in gold modified polyethylene was presented in Ref.²⁶. The bonding character of Au containing species is quite specific and its interpretation is greatly facilitated by considering relativistic effects²⁷⁻²⁹ which modify properties of Au considerably.

The next step in our research on cross-linking of PE chains is considering alternative metal atoms (M) and cross-linking of several PE chains with participation of several metal atoms eventually leading to two-dimensional, semi-planar monolayers. Modeling of properties of such structures is feasible at the molecular level by DFT methods providing that we have at our disposal a DFT functional suitable for calculations of BEs of C-M-C bonds in PEX-M-PEX chains with similar accuracy for a series of M atoms and at the same time functional well representing dispersion interactions between methylene groups of oligomer chains. In our paper on cross-linking of PE with Au atoms,¹³ we used the PBE0³⁰ functional combined with the D3(0)³¹ method for accounting dispersion contributions. Selection of PBE0, the hybrid version of the local PBE functional was based on benchmarking of its performance with respect to CCSD(T) in interactions of Cu, Ag, and Au with lone-pair ligands containing N, O, S, and P atoms^{32,33}. With this approach along with CCSD(T) calculations and careful consideration of relativistic effects, we have studied the bonding mechanism and binding energies of coinage atoms and particularly gold clusters with closed shell and open shell ligands^{17,32,33}. Using of the PBE0+D3(0) method is also supported by other benchmark calculations for, e.g., optimizing the geometry and calculations of the NMR shielding constants of a series of transition metal complexes³⁴. More recent benchmark results show that PBE0 + D3(0) functionals performed reasonably well for calculations of ligand dissociation energies of metal complexes³⁵ along with more recently developed MN15-L functionals³⁶.

Previous benchmarks of DFT functionals are of great help for further investigations of cross-linking of PE by a series of metal atoms. Nevertheless, according to Refs.^{35,37}, it appears that no single DFT method performs in a balanced way across sufficiently broad classes of compounds and properties even though the development in this field is impressive. In contrast with the wave function methods which allow stepwise improvement of methods leading towards accurate results upon extrapolation to the complete basis set limit (CBS), no such systematic

way is available with DFT. An analogy with wave-function methods has been introduced for DFT by Perdew *et al.*³⁸ with their “Jacob’s Ladder” representing a hierarchy of functionals, but the basic tool controlling the accuracy of DFT calculations remains their benchmarking with respect to experimental data (if available) or to high-level *ab initio* results extrapolated to the Complete Basis Set (CBS) limit. CCSD(T) with iterative calculations of single and double excitation amplitudes and the perturbative treatment of triples^{39,40} accompanied with inspection of the presence of large CCSD amplitudes serves the purpose reasonably well. Impressive presentation of the accumulated knowledge on the selection of DFT functionals and comparative benchmark results for 200 functionals has been published by Mardirossian and Head-Gordon⁴¹. Data sets include calculations of geometries, reaction and isomerization energies, bond dissociation energies, barrier heights, noncovalent interactions and case studies for transition metals chemistry and biologically relevant complexes. Detailed benchmarking was done by Truhlar’s group^{36,42} including the metal-ligand interactions and a wide spectrum of the ground state properties and excitation energies. Useful for the present project are benchmarks for DFT functionals in organometallic chemistry including the metal-ligand interactions^{43–49}, particularly those focusing to the metal-carbon bonds^{35–37,46–52}. Very extensive GMTKN55 data set for benchmarking DFT functionals for a wide spectrum of chemical properties was elaborated by Goerigk *et al.*⁵¹.

Large-scale research is available on functionals applicable to noncovalent and particularly dispersion interactions^{53–63} including papers stressing the importance of dispersion contributions in the organometallic chemistry^{53–55}. In the area of noncovalent interactions, there are essential extensive benchmark data produced by Hobza *et al.* in several steps^{60,61,64}. Although functionals for chemically diverse applications are available, we believe that benchmarking of functionals focused to calculations of BEs of C-M-C bonds with various metal atoms and dispersion interactions between oligomers representing cross-linked PE chains may improve the reliability

of modelling of properties of two-dimensional structures with several PE chains cross-linked with metal atoms and suggestion of novel materials. One example could be materials aimed at combined shielding effectiveness of lithium and polyethylene presumably applicable in the space research⁶⁵. Analogous benchmarks can be considered, e.g., in research on metal-mediated base pairs in the DNA nanotechnology¹⁰ with metal atoms inserted into the backbone of the DNA helix⁶⁶ and development of novel hybrid materials with metal encapsulated in a 1D chain⁶⁷.

Since no experimental data are available for binding energies of cross-linked PE-M-PE complexes, we benchmark the DFT functionals against CCSD(T) BEs. The smallest PE₃-M-PE₃ complexes are acceptable for testing of BEs for covalent C-M-C bonds but such model is not suitable for dispersion contributions. Our previous calculations¹³ of plain PEX···PEX models (no cross-linking) and PEX-Au-PEX complexes with up to 23 carbon atoms in a single oligomer chain show that BEs of larger complexes rise roughly linearly with the complex size. This is due to dispersion contributions which dominate in pairwise interactions between methylene groups and were found to be essential for forming well parallelized structures of PEX···PEX and PEX-Au-PEX oligomers. Recent calculations on transition metal-alkane interactions in Neese's group⁵⁵ also show that dispersion interactions are largely responsible for the thermodynamic stability of these complexes and can be modulated by increasing the number of carbons in the alkane chain. Computational demands of CCSD(T) calculations of larger PEX-M-PEX complexes are high but can be considerably alleviated by using the domain based local pair natural orbital approach, namely the DLPNO-CCSD(T) variant of CC methods, as defined and implemented by Neese and his group^{68,69}. Alternative approximate Coupled Cluster methods employing local approaches were introduced by Schütz and Werner⁷⁰ and more recently by Nagy and Kállay⁷¹. Tests and comparisons of these methods, which extend the applicability of CC methods considerably, indicate their good performance in molecular energetics including

some vexatious systems⁷². The reliability of DLPNO-CCSD(T) is well documented in original papers followed by several applications related to the present project. Since some applications show slight differences between CCSD(T) and DLPNO-CCSD(T),^{50,69} our first task is the comparison of BEs with canonical CCSD(T) and DLPNO-CCSD(T) methods for representative examples. Afterwards, wave function DLPNO-CCSD(T) BEs are used for benchmarking the series of DFT functionals for BEs of PEX-M-PEX complexes with selected metal atoms. We also address using of variants of the D3 correction to dispersion interactions, i.e. D3(0)³¹, D3(BJ)⁷³ and D3(BJ)-ABC⁷⁴ methods.

METHODS

All calculations were performed using the ORCA 4.2.1 program package^{75,76}. Geometry optimizations of pure parallel oligomer chains PEX \cdots PEX (the number of carbon atoms in each chain, X = 4, 5, 7, 9), and PE chains cross-linked by a single metal atom M, PEX-M-PEX, (M = Li, Be, Mg, Zn, Ag, Au; X = 3, 5, 7, 9) were performed with Unrestricted Kohn–Sham (UKS) orbitals employing the DFT with the PBE0 functional³⁰. Dispersion interactions were considered by Grimme’s dispersion model with the D3(0) damping^{31,77,78}. For reasons which will be explained later, PEX-Li-PEX complexes were optimized with the CAM-B3LYP/D3(0) functional⁷⁹. No symmetry constraints were imposed during the optimization process. Def2-TZVPP and def2-QZVPP basis sets⁸⁰ which incorporate scalar relativistic effective core potential (RECP) were used for both geometry optimizations and BEs calculations. For the optimization process TightSCF and TightOPT convergence criteria were used together with numerical integration Grid=4. For BEs calculations more accurate numerical integration Grid=6 was used along with TightSCF settings. CCSD(T), DLPNO-CCSD(T) and DLPNO-CCSD(T1) correlation energies were calculated using the default frozen core settings of the ORCA. The Resolution of Identity (RI) approximation was used for efficient treatment of two-electron integrals only for DLPNO-CCSD(T) and DLPNO-CCSD(T1) calculations. Therefore, BEs with Coupled

Cluster methods and all DFT functionals are compared at the same geometry for each specific complex and the basis set. This is a common and pragmatic approach, but we realize that the same geometry would not be fully optimal for each applied functional and method. Our test examples show that slight changes in the geometry do not affect the overall benchmarking results.

Binding energies of PEX \cdots PEX oligomer chains were calculated with respect to two PEX radicals. BEs of PEX-M-PEX complexes were calculated as the energy difference ΔE of the complex with respect to the PEX-M fragment and the PEX radical. Therefore, for the purpose of DFT benchmarking they represent breaking a single M-C bond in the metal cross-linked PEX-M-PEX complex. Energies of both fragments were calculated in the basis set of the complex at the geometry of the complex optimized as described above, i.e. presented BEs are corrected for the basis set superposition error (BSSE) in the framework of the counterpoise correction⁸¹.

Reference BEs used for benchmarking of DFT functionals result from DLPNO-CCSD(T)⁸² calculations with quasi-restricted orbitals^{83,84} (QRO) employing the TightPNO⁸⁵ settings in ORCA. In certain difficult cases indicated by large difference between canonical CCSD(T) and DLPNO-CCSD(T) in small PE3-M-PE3 complexes, we substituted the original perturbative treatment of triples by iterative calculations of triple excitation amplitudes, i.e. by the DLPNO-CCSD(T1) method, as introduced in Ref.⁸⁶ All benchmark results are single point calculations at optimized geometries as indicated above. Def2-TZVPP and def2-QZVPP basis sets were used for the extrapolation of BEs to the complete basis set (CBS) limit using Halkier et al. two-point extrapolation technique⁸⁷. Three versions of dispersion contributions combined with DFT functionals (excluding those in which dispersion term is already incorporated in the functional) were considered for model interactions of PEX \cdots PEX chains (X = 4, 5, 7, 9) as follows: Grimme's dispersion model with zero damping D3(0)^{31,77,78}; dispersion model with the Becke–

Johson damping function D3(BJ)⁷³ and finally, the dispersion model D3(BJ) with additional three-body dispersion terms, D3(BJ)-ABC⁸⁸.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

All complexes except of PEX-Li-PEX complexes were calculated at geometries optimized by methods described in the previous Section. Schematic structure of PEX-M-PEX complexes, similar for all metals is presented in **Figure 1**. Actual geometries for all PEX-M-PEX complexes are available as Archive in Supporting Information. We just note that the mutual orientation of two chains varies with the cross-linking metal atom and the number of CH₂ groups in each chain. The C-M-C bond angle in the PE3-Zn-PE3 complex was 180°, in accord with other studies on zinc di-alkyls, known also experimentally⁸⁹.

Figure 1. A typical structure of two PEX-M-PEX oligomer chains cross-linked by a metal atom (M). White, grey, and black spheres represent hydrogen, carbon, and metal atom, respectively. Inserted red part symbolize the smallest cross-linked structure used for the canonical CCSD(T) benchmarking.

The C-M-C bond angles for larger PEX-M-PEX complexes are lower, 170° - 176° for Be, Mg, and Zn containing complexes and 123° – 143° for complexes with Li, Ag, and Au complexes. Nicely parallel oligomer chains as observed in large PE23-Au-PE23 cross-linked species¹³ could not be reached for small PE3-M-PE3 complexes in which the dispersion interaction is

essentially missing. The impact of the metal atomic radius, hybridization of its atomic orbitals, steric repulsion of methyl groups and other parameters which may affect geometries of PEX-M-PEX complexes and C-M-C bonding characteristics will be analysed in the forthcoming paper.

CCSD(T) and DLPNO-CCSD(T) Binding Energies

Great feature of the DLPNO-CCSD(T) method is its applicability to much larger molecules than it is possible with canonical CCSD(T). Being an approximation to canonical CCSD(T),^{39,40} we feel that the reliability of BEs with DLPNO-CCSD(T) for our systems having covalent bonds accompanied with significant portion of dispersion interactions should be verified by comparing DLPNO-CCSD(T) and canonical CCSD(T) results at least for smaller PEX...PEX oligomers and cross-linked PEX-M-PEX complexes, still tractable by CCSD(T). We note that higher than negligible differences between DLPNO-CCSD(T) and canonical CCSD(T) results were observed in some specific situations before. Particularly relevant for our purpose are findings in Refs.^{35,50,52,68,69}. In general, the accuracy of DLPNO-CCSD(T) is sufficient for general chemistry applications, particularly reaction energies, with error of about 1 kJ/mol with the TightPNO⁸⁵ settings in ORCA. However, under some circumstances the errors of local correlation methods can be larger than the quoted averages. This may happen, e.g., in interactions of long parallel hydrocarbons⁸⁵ in which small individual errors can accumulate leading to eventually larger error than is the average and in some applications to open shell systems. Clearly, this is precisely the case in our study which prompts us to assess the accuracy of DLPNO-CCSD(T) for species studied in this work before its use as a reference for benchmarking DFT functionals. Preliminary results indicate that the error is mostly due to inaccuracies in the triples part of DLPNO-CCSD(T). Novel DLPNO developments show that an approximate iterative treatment of triples can reduce the error significantly, but computational demands are higher⁸⁶.

To assess the accuracy of DLPNO-CCSD(T), we used a simple model of pure PE4···PE4 dimer and small PE3-M-PE3 complexes, well tractable with canonical CCSD(T). The first one represents a model primarily for dispersion interactions and PE3-M-PE3 complexes add covalent C-M-C bonds. As indicators of potential problems with quasi-degeneracy in some complexes or fragments when using a single determinant QRO reference wave function we use the T1 diagnostic⁹⁰ and highest t2 amplitudes from canonical CCSD and DLPNO-CCSD results. Concerning quasi-degeneracy indicators for small complexes, highest values of the T1 diagnostics and t2 amplitudes from the CCSD wave function (def2-TZVPP basis set) were calculated for PE3-Ag and PE3-Au closed shell fragments, 0.022 and 0.020, respectively. CCSD t2 amplitudes were 0.10 and 0.09, still safely “green” in the Martin’s et al. classification of quasi degeneracy indicators⁹¹. T1 diagnostics and t2 amplitudes for doublet PE3-Ag-PE3 and PE3-Au-PE3 complexes were 0.018 and 0.07 (Ag) and 0.016 and 0.08 (Au). Checking the largest CCSD amplitudes along with the T1 diagnostics was stressed years ago⁹². Based on these data, we do not expect inaccuracies relevant for using of CCSD(T) results as a benchmark for DFT functionals. We note that these diagnostics were almost the same in the DLPNO-CCSD calculations.

The doublet PEX-Li-PEX complexes represent a specific case, where the PBE0+D3(0) optimization leads to an artificially symmetric geometry with two equivalent Li-C bonds. This represents a non-equilibrium structure with two semi-broken bonds corresponding to a transition state between two asymmetric (C—Li—C) minima. This was clearly visible from the CCSD t2 values ranging from 0.123 for PE3-Li-PE3 to 0.257 for PE7-Li-PE7. Upon reoptimizing the geometries with the CAM-B3LYP+D3(0) functional, T1 and t2 indicators for all PEX-Li-PEX complexes were lower than 0.012 and 0.05, respectively. We note that the T1 diagnostic and inspection of highest t2 amplitudes represent a simple internal way for detecting possible problems when using a single-determinant reference in CCSD(T). For more detailed analysis of indicators for non-dynamical correlation see, e.g., Refs. ^{91,93,94}.

Next, we will examine the accuracy of the DLPNO-CCSD(T) and DLPNO-CCSD(T1) approximations with respect to canonical CCSD and CCSD(T). Again, our model systems are PE4 \cdots PE4 and PE3-M-PE3 complexes. Results are collected in **Table 1**. BEs with DLPNO-CCSD agree with the data from canonical CCSD excellently for closed-shell complexes (M = Be, Mg, Zn) and for the open-shell complex PE3-Li-PE3. Slightly larger deviations occur in doublet complexes with Ag and Au, 3.75 and 2.07 kJ/mol, respectively (6.8 and 2.4% of the canonical CCSD BE). This creates some warning about the accuracy of the reference data particularly for Ag complexes. Nevertheless, considering much larger percentage errors with many DFT functionals, this appears to be still satisfactory for our purposes. However, upon including triples, the deviation for these complexes rise to 11.57 and 7.71 kJ/mol for PE3-Ag-PE3 and

Table 1. BEs (kJ/mol) for PE4 \cdots PE4^a and PE3-M-PE3^b complexes calculated with CCSD, CCSD(T), DLPNO-CCSD, DLPNO-CCSD(T) and DLPNO-CCSD(T1) methods with QRO orbitals as a reference using the def2-TZVPP basis set. The deviation of DLPNO-CCSD(T) and DLPNO-CCSD(T1) (in parenthesis) from CCSD(T) is in the last column.

Complexes ^c	CCSD(T)	CCSD	DLPNO-CCSD	DLPNO-CCSD(T)	DLPNO-CCSD(T1)	Error [%]
PE4 \cdots PE4	-8.62	-6.12	-5.88	-7.94	-8.03	7.89 (6.84)
PE3-Be-PE3	-370.73	-363.91	-364.47	-370.97	-371.38	0.07 (0.17)
PE3-Mg-PE3	-242.28	-234.51	-235.37	-242.54	-243.03	0.11 (0.31)
PE3-Zn-PE3	-277.70	-267.9	-269.56	-278.31	-279.49	0.22 (0.64)
PE3-Li-PE3	-37.52	-34.78	-34.25	-36.51	-36.58	2.69 (2.50)
PE3-Ag-PE3	-71.29	-54.97	-51.22	-59.72	-65.06	16.22 (8.74)
PE3-Au-PE3	-100.04	-85.65	-83.58	-92.33	-95.44	7.71 (4.60)

^aBEs are calculated with respect to fragments 2PE4.

^bBEs are calculated with respect to fragments PE3-M + PE3.

^cComplexes PE4 \cdots PE4, PE3-Be-PE3, PE3-Mg-PE3 and PE3-Zn-PE3 are singlets, their fragments are doublets; PE3-Li-PE3, PE3-Ag-PE3, and PE3-Au-PE3 are doublets, their PE3-M and PE3 fragments are singlets and doublets, respectively.

PE3-Au-PE3, respectively. Such deviation is large, representing 16.2 and 7.7 % of the CCSD(T) BEs for these complexes. Deviation of 7.9 % for the weakly bound PE4...PE4 complex appears large as well, but BE for this small complex is low and differs with the two methods just by 0.68 kJ/mol. As suggested in Ref ⁸⁶ a remedy for treating inaccuracies of DLPNO-CCSD(T) results is iterative treatment of triples, namely using the DLPNO-CCSD(T1) method (nomenclature taken from the ORCA input file). This is nicely seen in **Figure 2** which shows the deviation of DLPNO-CCSD(T) and DLPNO-CCSD(T1) absolute energies from canonical CCSD(T) for PE4...PE4 and PE3-M-PE3 complexes and corresponding fragments calculated with the def2-TZVPP basis set.

Figure 2. Deviation of DLPNO-CCSD(T) (A) and DLPNO-CCSD(T1) (B) absolute energies (a.u.) from canonical CCSD(T) for PE4...PE4 and PE3-M-PE3 complexes (M = Li, Be, Mg, Zn, Ag, Au) and their fragments, calculated in the geometry of the complex. Colors: blue, red, and green are for the complex and fragments in their own basis sets; yellow and purple are for fragments in the basis set of the complex.

Figure 2 also reveals that absolute energies errors for PE3-Zn-PE3 and its fragments are not small. Small difference between BEs with DLPNO-CCSD(T) and CCSD(T) follows from the error compensation in PE3-Zn-PE3 and its fragment, which is not the case with complexes of Ag and Au. Detailed insight into the comparison of the DLPNO-CCSD(T) and iterative DLPNO-CCSD(T1) including the basis set dependence gives **Table 2**. Differences of BEs with the two DLPNO methods do not rise when going from the simplest PE3-M-PE3 complexes to

the larger PE9-M-PE9 ones. BEs with DLPNO-CCSD(T) and DLPNO-CCSD(T1) for most problematic Ag complexes differ by 5.5 and 4.7 kJ/mol for PE3-Ag-PE3 and PE9-Ag-PE9, respectively (4.6% of the DLPNO-CCSD(T1) value for the larger complex in the CBS limit).

Analogous difference for PE9-Au-PE9 complex is 2.8 kJ/mol (2.2%). For all other complexes, the differences are much smaller. The basis set effect on absolute values of BEs is significant. The difference between BEs with the def2-TZVPP basis set and at the CBS value is larger than 20 kJ/mol in some cases.

Table 2. BEs (kJ/mol) with DLPNO-CCSD(T) and DLPNO-CCSD(T1) methods for PE3-M-PE3 and PE9-M-PE9 (M = Be, Mg, Zn, Li, Ag, Au) complexes. def2-TZVPP and def2-QZVPP basis sets used for the extrapolation to the CBS limit. BEs with respect to PEX-M and PEX fragments.

Complexes	DLPNO-CCSD(T)			DLPNO-CCSD(T1)		
	TZVPP	QZVPP	CBS	TZVPP	QZVPP	CBS
PE4...PE4	-7.9	-9.3	-10.3	-8.0	-9.4	-10.4
PE9...PE9	-22.5	-25.1	-27.0	-22.7	-25.3	-27.3
PE3-Be-PE3	-371.0	-384.1	-393.6	-371.4	-384.5	-394.1
PE9-Be-PE9	-386.5	-400.4	-410.5	-387.2	-401.1	-411.3
PE3-Mg-PE3	-242.5	-250.9	-257.1	-243.0	-251.5	-257.6
PE9-Mg-PE9	-259.0	-268.1	-274.7	-259.7	-268.9	-275.6
PE3-Zn-PE3	-278.3	-290.1	-298.7	-279.5	-291.5	-300.2
PE9-Zn-PE9	-293.0	-305.4	-314.5	-294.4	-307.2	-316.4
PE3-Li-PE3	-36.5	-39.9	-42.3	-36.6	-39.9	-42.4
PE9-Li-PE9	-56.5	-61.2	-64.6	-56.7	-61.4	-64.8
PE3-Ag-PE3	-59.7	-67.6	-73.4	-65.1	-73.1	-79.0
PE9-Ag-PE9	-79.0	-89.2	-96.6	-83.7	-93.9	-101.3
PE3-Au-PE3	-92.3	-101.6	-108.4	-95.4	-104.8	-111.6
PE9-Au-PE9	-106.3	-117.5	-125.6	-109.1	-120.3	-128.4

In summary, DLPNO-CCSD(T1) improves the performance of DLPNO-CCSD(T) for some problematic cases considerably. In their original papers, Neese *et al.*^{69,86} report that problems

can be expected for open-shell systems and for dispersion interactions. This is partly confirmed by our data for open-shell systems, not so much for dispersion interactions which contribute to the enhancement of BEs with increased length of the PE chain. Energies in **Figure 2** indicate that the largest individual deviations from canonical CCSD(T) exhibit PE3-Ag-PE3 and PE3-Au-PE3 complexes (doublets) but, to a lesser extent, also their closed-shell fragments. The T1 diagnostic and t2 amplitudes for both complexes and their fragments do not signalize a problem. Some warning might arise from slightly higher expectation values of the spin S^2 operator with starting UHF orbitals (0.96 and 0.83, respectively) which are subsequently transformed to QRO orbitals. Relatively high deviation of absolute energies for the closed-shell PE3-Zn-PE3 complex and its fragment is unexpected. When talking about BEs of our complexes, we note both the closed-shell and the open-shell (doublet) species participate in all BEs. The important factor is compensation of errors, which is less effective for doublet complexes containing Ag and Au atoms. Therefore, benchmarking of DFT functionals for these complexes (and for the consistency also for doublet PEX-Li-PEX complexes) will be based on DLPNO-CCSD(T1) results, as suggested in Ref. ⁶⁹. Since BEs for Be, Mg and Zn containing closed shell complexes with DLPNO-CCSD(T) and DLPNO-CCSD(T1) differ by less than 2 kJ/mol (no more than 0.6 %) these complexes were benchmarked with respect to the former method. Computational time for DLPNO-CCSD(T1) calculations in the original paper⁸⁶ is reported to be about five times longer than for DLPNO-CCSD(T). The timing for our systems rises linearly upon extending the length of the PEX chain with both DLPNO-CCSD(T) and DLPNO-CCSD(T1) methods, but the slope is about four times higher for DLPNO-CCSD(T1).

Related paper on the accuracy assessment of DLPNO-CCSD(T) in calculations of reaction energies and barriers for a broad range of open- and closed-shell reactions of organic molecules was published⁹⁵ just before finishing the present work. Since our work focuses on complexes with metal-carbon bonds not included in the above study, the two papers are to some extent

complementary. We have tested using tighter thresholds in DLPNO-CCSD(T) as suggested in Ref.⁹⁵ for some smaller complexes. Changing the default TCutMKN parameter in ORCA from 10^{-3} to 10^{-4} and 10^{-5} brought no significant improvement of the accuracy of BEs. Tighter setting for TCutPNO improved BEs by about 3% in comparison to BEs obtained with default settings but the memory requirements increased by a factor of three.

DFT dispersion energy contributions to binding energies.

The importance of the dispersion energy contributions in pure PEX \cdots PEX and PEX-Au-PEX complexes (with X up to 23) with one to three cross-linking gold atoms was discussed in detail in our previous paper^{13,14}. The findings confirm expected trend, namely that BEs rise almost linearly with the number of C atoms in the PEX oligomer chain. Dispersion terms in long enough PE chains not only stabilize the complex but also contribute to parallel structures of PE \cdots PE chains. Previous DFT calculations were performed with the PBE0 functional and D3(0) dispersion contributions. Here, we compare BEs for PEX \cdots PEX complexes with D3(0), D3(BJ) and D3(BJ)-ABC dispersion terms and DLPNO-CCSD(T) using geometries optimized by the PBE(0)/D3(0) method with the def2-TZVPP basis set (see **Figure 5** in Ref. 13). DLPNO-CCSD(T) method can be safely used as a benchmark, since BE with DLPNO-CCSD(T) differs from the canonical CCSD(T) result for PE4 \cdots PE4 by only 0.68 kJ/mol. **Table 3** shows that BEs with the three methods for accounting dispersion interactions differ significantly but trends upon extending the size of the PEX chain are represented correctly. Deviations of BEs with the PBE0 functional from DLPNO-CCSD(T) results decrease with higher level of treating the dispersion interaction. Yet, with PBE0/D3(BJ)-ABC the difference is 2.9 kJ/mol for PE4 \cdots PE4 and 5.5 kJ/mol for PE9 \cdots PE9, i.e., 24%.

Table 3. BEs (kJ/mol) of parallel PEX \cdots PEX ($X = 4, 5, 7, 9$) oligomer chains with the PBE0 DFT functional and D3(0), D3(BJ), and D3(BJ)-ABC dispersion contributions compared with DLPNO-CCSD(T) results using the def2-TZVPP basis set. Geometries optimized by the PBE0/D3(0) method.

Complexes	D3(0)	D3(BJ)	D3(BJ)-ABC	DLPNO-CCSD(T)	DLPNO-CCSD	DLPNO-MP2
PE4 \cdots PE4	-12.3	-11.2	-10.8	-7.9	-5.9	-9.2
PE5 \cdots PE5	-16.3	-14.9	-14.3	-11.0	-8.2	-12.9
PE7 \cdots PE7	-24.2	-22.2	-21.2	-16.8	-12.8	-20.0
PE9 \cdots PE9	-31.7	-29.4	-28.0	-22.5	-17.0	-26.7

Benchmarking DFT functionals.

Selection of functionals for most DFT applications is greatly facilitated by employing benchmark studies based on extended databases for main group thermochemistry, kinetics, catalysis or noncovalent interactions. As mentioned above, our task is to a certain extent problem oriented, i.e., we need a reliable method for representing various C-M-C bonds with balanced accuracy and, at the same time, dispersion interactions with gradually longer PE chains. Since we plan large scale applications, we primarily focused on Jacob’s Ladder rung 4 functionals.

Based on results in **Tables 1 – 3** and the preliminary analysis of the performance of several DFT functionals, we present the benchmarking in three steps. First, we study the performance of the DFT functionals for BEs of gradually larger pure PEX \cdots PEX chains in which dominate dispersion interactions (**Table 4**). In the next step, we calculate the BEs of closed-shell PEX-M-PEX complexes with the cross-linking Be, Mg, and Zn metal atoms (**Table 5**) all having the ns^2 valence electronic structure. DFT functionals are benchmarked against the DLPNO-CCSD(T) BEs. Finally, we analyze doublet complexes with Li, Ag and Au atoms cross-linking PEX chains (**Table 6**), this time against the DLPNO-CCSD(T1) BEs. For all complexes, we follow the Absolute Percentage Error (APE) with gradually increasing size of each oligomer chain having 4 – 9 carbon atoms in PEX \cdots PEX chains and 3 – 9 atoms in chains of PEX-M-

PEX complexes. Keeping in mind the different convergence with the basis set size for a series of DFT functionals and for DLPNO-CCSD(T) BEs, benchmarking is uniformly performed with respect to the CBS limit for the DLPNO-CC binding energies. We note that general conclusions would not be seriously affected when using just the smaller def2-TZVPP basis set for the DFT calculations (as illustrated by data with def2-TZVPP, def2-QZVPP basis sets and the CBS limit for PEX \cdots PEX complexes in the form of the MAPE bar diagram and MAPE bar diagrams for each individual metallic atom in PEX-M-PEX complexes, see the Supporting Information, Figure S1. Finally, we present a comprehensive insight on the performance of DFT functionals in the form of MAPE for all PEX-M-PEX complexes with M = Li, Be, Mg, Zn, Ag, Au (Figure S2) and MAPE of all metal containing complexes plus PEX \cdots PEX complexes, Figure S3.

Before going into deeper analysis of the performance of DFT functionals we wish to address the possible effects of the geometry optimization on benchmarked BEs. Therefore, we have investigated the effect of geometry on BEs of the smallest (PE3-M-PE3 and PE4 \cdots PE4) complexes. As an alternative to the PBE0/D3(0) geometry optimizations these structures were re-optimized using the CAM-B3LYP and ω B97X-D3 functionals and the resulting BEs were compared to one another and to the original BEs based on the PBE0/D3(0) geometries (apart from Li complexes which represent a specific problem, as discussed above). The changes in BEs calculated at the CCSD(T), DLPNO-CCSD(T)/(T1) and DFT level with 6 of the top performing functionals (CAM-B3LYP, ω B97X-D3, PW6B95, M06, TPSS0, PBE0, all including the dispersion contribution) due to changes in geometry were typically of the order of 1 – 2% for all systems. Resulting changes exhibit the standard deviation of 1.7%. Slightly larger spread of binding energies was observed for M06 and PW6B95 functionals with standard deviations of 3.1% and 2.5%, respectively. These changes of BEs are negligible in the context of the present study. Therefore, the geometries obtained as described above are considered as satisfactory.

PEX \cdots PEX complexes.

Dominant contribution to BEs in PEX \cdots PEX complexes comes from dispersion interactions.

Table 4. Absolute percentage errors of BEs with DFT functionals^a for PEX \cdots PEX complexes ($X = 4, 5, 7, 9$) with respect to DLPNO-CCSD(T) CBS limit^b.

Functional	PE4 \cdots PE4	PE5 \cdots PE5	PE7 \cdots PE7	PE9 \cdots PE9
BP86	6.2	1.2	3.5	9.2
BLYP	3.0	5.4	6.8	11.0
OLYP	1.8	0.8	0.5	0.9
mPWLYP	11.0	8.1	4.3	4.9
PBE	13.5	11.2	8.2	9.4
RPBE	12.8	9.2	5.2	5.3
REVPBE	10.2	10.3	9.4	11.6
B3LYP	6.1	7.0	7.5	10.8
B3PW	8.9	5.2	1.7	2.7
PW6B95	10.1	17.8	19.8	22.7
BHANDHLYP	2.1	1.8	1.4	3.7
PBE0	6.9	5.7	4.1	5.6
TPSS	2.6	2.7	3.9	2.6
TPSSh	1.6	1.5	2.4	0.9
TPSS0	4.9	5.0	5.7	4.1
B97M-D3BJ	14.9	16.1	16.6	20.4
SCAN	2.2	2.4	1.9	0.5
M06	1.4	1.5	5.1	10.4
M06-L	2.1	3.0	6.0	8.8
M06-2X	12.9	10.3	7.7	5.3
ω B97X-D3	17.5	19.0	20.4	23.3
ω B97X-D3BJ	14.9	15.3	15.2	17.8
ω B97M-D3BJ	16.2	16.0	16.3	19.4
CAM-B3LYP	1.8	1.7	1.4	3.6
B2PLYP-D3	3.7	2.2	1.0	2.2

^aIf not noted explicitly, functionals are supplemented by D3(BJ)-ABC dispersion contributions. No explicit D3 contribution is added to M06, M06-L and M06-2X functionals.

^bAll BEs at the CBS limit extrapolated from def2-TZVPP and def2-QZVPP basis sets.

In general, several DFT functionals used in the present study perform for PEX \cdots PEX complexes ($X = 4, 5, 7, 9$) reasonably well, considering the accuracy needed for comparisons of different metals cross-linking PEX chains. Absolute percentage error of BEs with respect to DLPNO-CCSD(T) presented in **Table 4** is lower than 4% with seven DFT functionals

(OLYP⁹⁶⁻⁹⁸, TPSSh⁹⁹, SCAN¹⁰⁰, CAM-B3LYP, BHANDHLYP¹⁰¹, B2PLYP-D3¹⁰², TPSS¹⁰³) for complexes of any size, but the order is different for short and long chains.

Overall, OLYP is the best almost for all PEX···PEX complexes, CAM-B3LYP performs excellently for short chains and is slightly less accurate for longer chains but may serve as a good compromise. PBE0/D3(BJ)-ABC performs still acceptably, which agrees with good performance of this functional for alkane dimers⁴¹. Bar diagram with Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) for all PEX···PEX complexes is in **Figure S1**. We note, that hybrid meta-GGA M06, M06-L and M06-2X functionals¹⁰⁴⁻¹⁰⁶ which are implicitly parameterized also for noncovalent interactions perform better with no additional D3 contributions in PEX···PEX complexes. This point has been previously discussed, e.g., in refs. ^{56,58,107}. Our test calculations reveal that appending M06, M06-L and M06-2X functionals by the D3(0) term over-bind PEX···PEX complexes considerably (M06 functional by 56 - 70%; much less M06-2X functional, by 10 – 21%). Oppositely, pure M06-2X functional under-binds PE9···PE9 only by 1.5 kJ/mol. No spectacular performance for PEX···PEX complexes exhibit ω B97X-D3^{108,109}, ω B97X-D3BJ¹¹⁰ and ω B97M-D3BJ¹¹⁰ range-separated hybrid functionals, even though they contain the dispersion energy contributions. This is somewhat surprising. For example, ω B97X-D3 belongs among functionals recommended by other authors, see e. g. Refs. ^{56,58,108,111}. The B2PLYP-D3 fifth rung method³¹ considered as the most balanced approach for noncovalent interactions^{58,61} belongs among best performers also for PEX···PEX complexes but is more time consuming than other rung 4 functionals tested in this work particularly with larger basis sets. We note that the cost of B2LYP could be reduced by using the Resolution of Identity (RI) in the MP2-like step.

Closed-shell PEX-Be-PEX, PEX-Mg-PEX, and PEX-Zn-PEX complexes

For this set of complexes, small or large, almost all tested functionals perform excellently. **Table 5** shows that the highest deviation from the DLPNO-CCSD(T) benchmark just slightly

Table 5. Absolute percentage errors of BEs with DFT functionals^a for PEX-M-PEX complexes (M = Be, Mg, Zn; X = 3, 5, 7, 9) with respect to DLPNO-CCSD(T) CBS data^b.

Functional	PEX-Be-PEX				PEX-Mg-PEX				PEX-Zn-PEX				
	X	3	5	7	9	3	5	7	9	3	5	7	9
BP86		4.4	4.4	4.2	4.1	6.6	5.5	4.9	4.4	2.1	1.5	1.0	0.6
BLYP		4.7	5.1	5.0	5.0	8.5	7.9	7.5	7.0	6.8	6.5	6.3	5.9
OLYP		4.5	5.0	5.0	5.0	8.7	8.0	7.6	6.8	3.9	3.3	3.1	2.7
mPWLYP		4.0	4.8	4.9	4.9	8.2	8.4	8.3	7.6	7.6	8.2	8.1	7.6
PBE		3.3	3.6	3.6	3.5	5.7	5.4	5.2	4.5	1.2	1.6	1.5	0.9
RPBE		5.4	5.6	5.7	5.6	7.1	5.4	5.0	3.7	0.2	0.7	0.8	1.5
REVPBE		6.6	6.7	6.6	6.4	10.1	9.2	8.8	7.9	5.1	4.8	4.5	3.8
B3LYP		3.2	3.5	3.5	3.5	6.7	6.3	6.0	5.4	5.3	5.1	4.9	4.5
B3PW		3.6	3.5	3.4	3.4	5.7	4.8	4.3	3.8	1.5	1.0	0.6	0.2
PW6B95		1.2	1.1	1.1	1.1	2.8	2.5	2.2	1.9	1.7	1.9	1.6	1.1
BHANDHLYP		3.3	3.6	3.7	3.7	7.1	6.9	6.7	6.3	6.2	6.0	5.9	5.6
PBE0		3.0	3.1	3.2	3.1	5.6	5.2	5.0	4.3	1.3	1.5	1.3	0.7
TPSS		5.7	6.1	6.0	5.9	8.1	7.7	7.2	6.5	3.1	3.2	2.9	2.2
TPSSh		5.3	5.5	5.5	5.3	7.9	7.4	7.0	6.1	3.1	3.1	2.8	2.1
TPSS0		4.6	4.8	4.8	4.8	7.2	6.7	6.4	5.8	2.5	2.4	2.2	1.7
B97M-D3BJ		1.4	1.6	1.7	1.7	2.3	0.4	0.1	0.7	2.4	3.4	3.6	4.0
SCAN		5.1	5.0	5.0	5.0	6.7	5.8	5.7	5.4	1.6	1.5	1.4	1.1
M06		1.7	3.1	5.0	7.2	0.4	1.0	0.5	0.1	2.5	1.3	1.9	1.9
M06-L		4.3	3.4	3.8	3.7	5.1	4.1	4.1	3.7	3.0	2.2	2.5	1.9
M06-2X		0.2	0.2	0.5	0.8	4.1	3.5	3.9	4.6	5.1	4.6	5.0	5.2
ωB97X-D3		0.4	0.1	0.2	0.5	1.5	1.8	2.1	3.0	5.1	5.1	5.3	6.2
ωB97X-D3BJ		1.0	1.2	1.2	1.3	3.5	4.2	4.5	5.3	6.8	7.1	7.2	7.8
ωB97M-D3BJ		8.6	8.0	7.9	8.0	10.6	9.8	9.8	10.2	7.2	6.2	6.2	6.7
CAM-B3LYP		1.3	1.7	1.7	1.7	3.4	3.6	3.4	3.0	1.3	1.8	1.6	1.2
B2PLYP-D3		3.0	3.3	3.2	3.3	6.7	6.5	6.2	5.9	5.5	5.4	5.3	4.9

^{a,b} See footnotes to table 4.

exceeds 10% for PEX-Mg-PEX complexes. This is much less than are APEs for PEX⋯PEX complexes. Here, for PEX-Be-PEX, PEX-Mg-PEX, and PEX-Zn-PEX complexes the situation is more favorable. Uniformly low APEs for all complexes with Be, Mg, and Zn cross-linking

atoms show hybrid (PW6B95¹¹²) and range-separated hybrid functionals (CAM-B3LYP) with errors less than 4%, even though they do not rank among best five in all cases. The ω B97X-D3 functional performs excellently for PEX-Be-PEX and PEX-Mg-PEX complexes with slightly higher APE (5.1 – 6.2%) for Zn complexes. Balanced performance exhibit also Minnesota functionals. The highest APE with M06-L and M06-2X is 5.1 and 5.2% for some of Mg and Zn complexes. Interestingly, augmenting M06-type functionals with explicit dispersion D3(0) contribution is profitable for Be, Mg, and Zn complexes reducing APE by 0.5 – 3.5%, in contrast to PEX \cdots PEX complexes. We have no explanation for this result. B3PW^{113–115} and B97M-D3BJ¹¹⁰ functionals perform excellently, good performer for closed shell PEX-M-PEX complexes is also common PBE0 functional.

PEX-Li-PEX, PEX-Ag-PEX, and PEX-Au-PEX doublet complexes

In contrast to the nice performance of DFT functionals for BEs of PEX-M-PEX complexes with closed shell Be, Mg, and Zn atoms, data in **Table 6** indicate that finding of DFT functionals for calculations of BEs for open-shell PEX-M-PEX complexes with similar accuracy across selected atoms is not straightforward. The most problematic is the selection of DFT functionals for Li complexes with prevailing red columns in **Table 6**. Reports on the performance of DFT for Li containing species are controversial. For example, the error in the homolytic dissociation of a simple molecule, LiH, was less than 3% at the BP86/TZ2P level when compared with the experimental value¹¹⁶. We also note that CCSD(T) as the reference for binding energies of LiH works excellently¹¹⁷. Contrary to this predictions of multipole moments of LiH, NaLi, and CH₃Li by DFT methods¹¹⁸ (a more demanding task) were found as difficult cases for DFT, although these molecules do not show particularly multireference character, which is also true with our PEX-Li-PEX complexes. On the other hand, analogous Be compounds which are also difficult for multipole moments do not appear as problematic for BEs of PEX-Be-PEX complexes.

Best performers for Li complexes are ω B97X-D3, CAM-B3LYP and B2PLYP-D3 (range-separated hybrid functionals and perturbatively corrected double-hybrid functional, respectively) having relatively high errors with respect to the DLPNO-CCSD(T1) CBS benchmark, but still lower than 15%. For Li complexes, the best performer is the ω B97X-D3 functional. It also performs reasonably well across all metals (less so for Zn), but the average APE for PEX...PEX complexes is 20%. The point is that dispersion interactions do not dominate in metal bound PEX-M-PEX complexes so that the overall performance is not affected too much, at least for not too long PEX chains. Finally, B2PLYP-D3, the one belonging to the rung 5 of the hierarchy of functionals, which performs well for Li is not particularly good for Mg, Zn and performs poorly for Ag containing complexes. Looking at rows with the CAM-B3LYP/D3(BJ)-ABC functional in **Tables 5** and **6**, it performs satisfactorily for Li complexes, and is excellent for

Table 6. Absolute percentage errors of BEs with DFT functionals^a for PEX-M-PEX complexes (M = Li, Ag, Au; X = 3, 5, 7, 9) with respect to DLPNO-CCSD(T1) CBS data^b.

Functional	PEX-Li-PEX				PEX-Ag-PEX				PEX-Au-PEX				
	X	3	5	7	9	3	5	7	9	3	5	7	9
BP86		34.1	55.9	47.2	39.4	40.4	34.7	36.5	35.4	18.3	18.5	19.5	19.4
BLYP		39.2	58.4	47.7	40.2	23.0	16.6	18.8	18.9	0.9	0.7	1.4	1.9
OLYP		47.7	60.0	48.7	40.7	20.7	18.1	21.3	20.1	6.3	6.7	7.8	8.5
mPWLYP		33.9	48.0	35.8	28.4	17.9	7.7	8.3	8.7	3.2	6.3	5.9	5.1
PBE		39.0	53.3	41.9	33.8	36.3	26.9	27.5	26.5	16.0	13.0	13.1	13.5
RPBE		66.4	74.1	59.9	52.0	46.8	41.0	42.0	39.7	26.4	26.0	26.4	26.9
REVPBE		35.1	52.1	42.8	35.3	23.8	18.8	21.8	21.2	5.6	5.3	6.2	7.2
B3LYP		16.6	31.7	26.1	22.2	9.5	5.7	8.4	8.8	2.9	2.9	2.4	1.6
B3PW		15.2	29.5	25.6	21.4	19.6	17.3	20.6	19.6	8.8	9.7	10.8	10.9
PW6B95		15.4	28.6	27.2	21.6	8.4	5.7	11.5	9.6	1.3	0.9	0.9	1.1
BHANDHLYP		15.5	16.0	13.5	13.1	23.1	22.0	18.0	16.7	17.8	16.8	16.6	15.5
PBE0		15.3	22.2	17.9	14.9	13.3	11.3	11.4	11.0	6.7	5.3	5.7	6.4
TPSS		24.1	39.2	30.6	23.0	28.6	21.9	23.5	21.9	9.3	8.2	8.9	9.4
TPSSh		14.1	27.4	21.6	16.2	19.8	15.0	17.4	16.3	5.9	5.3	6.3	7.0
TPSS0		14.1	18.7	15.2	12.2	7.8	5.5	8.6	7.5	2.3	2.4	3.0	3.5
B97M-D3BJ		26.9	49.3	42.7	37.3	31.5	27.9	30.2	29.0	12.5	13.1	13.2	13.4
SCAN		13.6	32.2	25.3	18.5	39.6	29.6	28.7	26.5	20.1	16.8	16.1	15.0
M06		1.1	22.1	19.2	15.4	1.5	5.0	3.5	2.9	10.5	8.9	10.8	11.1

M06-L	18.8	31.2	27.8	20.5	9.9	11.5	11.9	9.8	8.9	7.1	8.6	8.0
M06-2X	13.4	18.3	17.0	12.4	20.4	17.2	13.3	15.4	15.5	13.9	15.2	15.7
ω B97X-D3	3.8	2.4	4.9	5.6	3.0	3.6	1.1	2.2	1.6	1.8	1.1	0.7
ω B97X-D3BJ	29.0	28.8	26.7	25.9	7.2	9.3	14.5	14.1	10.0	11.2	11.5	12.8
ω B97M-D3BJ	13.0	16.4	16.4	15.8	6.3	4.6	1.1	1.5	3.1	2.9	2.4	0.9
CAM-B3LYP	12.0	14.0	11.6	10.9	0.7	2.4	0.7	1.1	2.1	3.1	2.6	1.7
B2PLYP-D3	8.0	14.5	11.8	10.0	34.5	39.2	28.9	27.7	16.6	16.0	16.2	15.9

^{a,b} See footnotes to table 4.

Ag, Au, and for all closed-shell complexes as well. Therefore, along with ω B97X-D3, it represents a reasonable compromise across all PEX-M-PEX species and performs well also for pure PEX \cdots PEX complexes bound primarily by dispersion interactions. The two range-separated hybrid functionals ω B97X-D3, CAM-B3LYP are good candidates for applications to problems in which relatively accurate and balanced calculations of BEs for species having various C-M-C bonds are required. Acceptable is also TPSS0¹¹⁹ (although with APE 15% or slightly higher for some complexes with Li), which is slightly less time consuming. Unfortunately, we can hardly extend our findings for species containing Li-C bonds (our most problematic case) to other Li containing molecules. For example, benchmarks for BEs of molecules with Li-S bonds important in lithium-sulfur battery research indicate that the best performer is the PW6B95 functional¹²⁰. Data in **Table 6** show that for PEX-Li-PEX complexes is APE with the PW6B95 functional as high as 28% but it performs well for complexes with Ag and Au.

We note the striking difference between the performance of the ω B97X-D3 and ω B97X-D3(BJ) functionals as is seen in **Table 6**. This large difference is not in fact caused by the inclusion of the Becke–Johnson damping in the empirical dispersion correction. Both the exchange–correlation and the dispersion parts of these functionals are parametrized differently and the potential confusion can be attributed to somewhat unfortunate naming. Interestingly, the dispersion con-

tributions of the ω B97X-D3(BJ) functional to binding energies are more than doubled as compared to the ω B97X-D3 functional, leading to over-binding and hence also to its comparatively poorer performance.

It is rather difficult to briefly summarize the diverse results for best DFT functionals for binding energies of PEX \cdots PEX, closed-shell and open-shell PEX-M-PEX complexes. A comprehensive view on the performance of DFT functionals can be based on the Mean Absolute Percentage Errors (MAPE). Our testing is based on errors of BEs of complexes with all investigated atoms and the size of the oligomer chain (denoted as the CMC-D dataset) in comparison with benchmarks, CBS limit DLPNO-CCSD(T) or DLPNO-CCSD(T1) data. A detailed insight with MAPEs individually for each cross-linking atom offers Figure S1. MAPEs for all functionals with all PEX \cdots PEX and PEX-M-PEX complexes and their selected combinations within the CMC-D dataset with def2-TZVPP and def2-QZVPP basis sets and the CBS limit can be found in **Figures S2 and S3**. Excluding for a while PEX \cdots PEX and problematic Li complexes from the CMC-D dataset, we find six functionals which exhibit MAPE lower than 5%, namely CAM-B3LYP, ω B97X-D3, PW6B95, M06, TPSS0, B3LYP¹¹³. Slightly larger MAPE show PBE0 and M06L functionals. Respective bar diagrams are in **Figure 3**. Combining best performers for Li complexes with those for PEX-M-PEX complexes with Be, Mg, Zn, Ag, and Au (that means combining data from **Tables 5, 6 and Figure 3**), we suggest ω B97X-D3, CAM-B3LYP functionals as good candidates for extensive applications to cross-linking of several PE chains with a variety of metal atoms. The same follows from MAPE for all metallic PEX-M-PEX complexes which is lower than 5% for ω B97X-D3 and CAM-B3LYP functionals (see Figure S2). In systems with gradually increased polymer size with larger contribution of dispersion interactions, we suggest the CAM-B3LYP functional which outperforms the ω B97X-D3 functional.

Figure 3. MAPE(%) of BEs with DFT functionals for PEX-M-PEX complexes ($X = 3, 5, 7, 9$) with respect to CBS DLPNO-CCSD(T) ($M = \text{Be, Mg, and Zn}$) and DLPNO-CCSD(T1) (Ag, and Au) benchmark data. CBS limit BEs are extrapolated from def2-TZVPP and def2-QZVPP basis set results. If not noted explicitly, functionals are supplemented by D3(BJ)-ABC dispersion contributions. No explicit D3 contribution is added to M06, M06-L and M06-2X functionals.

A possible approach which may help finding suitable functionals is suggested as follows. First, start with the most problematic case, i.e., PEX-Li-PEX complexes in our case. Afterwards, try to combine the best functionals which result from the first step with those which work for the less demanding problems. Based on this approach, ω B97X-D3 and CAM-B3LYP functionals appear as reasonable candidates for larger applications which were mentioned above. With functionals well representing dispersion interactions in long and (almost) parallel chains we expect linear dependence of BEs with the oligomer size. This is demonstrated for ω B97X-D3 and CAM-B3LYP/D3(BJ)-ABC functionals in Figure S4 (also for PBE0/D3(BJ)-ABC; note that PBE0/D(0) was used for the geometry optimization). The correlation factor is higher than 0.9; the slope lies between 3.2 for Be complexes and 4.7 $\text{kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}/X$ for Li complexes (the ω B97X-D3 functional) and between 2.3 and 4.1 $\text{kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}/X$ for Be and Li complexes (the CAM-B3LYP+D3(BJ)-ABC functional), respectively. Analogous dependence of BEs on the

PEX···PEX and PEX-M-PEX complex size with DLPNO-CCSD(T)/(T1) methods and def2-TZVPP, def2-QZVPP basis sets and the CBS limit is available in Figure S5. Binding energies of all complexes with DLPNO-CCSD(T) or DLPNO-CCSD(T1) methods are presented in Tables S1 – S4 of the Supporting Information.

CONCLUSIONS.

Selecting functionals suitable for calculations of BEs with acceptable and balanced accuracy for complexes bound by concerned effect of covalent C-M-C bonds and dispersion interactions between oligomer chains with a series of metal atoms may need more detailed care than is a common practice for the mainstream chemistry applications.

Based on the present case study of 25 DFT functionals, the favorable candidates for extensive calculations of a series of PEX-M-PEX complexes with different PEX oligomer chain are ω B97X-D3 and CAM-B3LYP/D3(BJ)-ABC functionals with MAPE lower than 5% across six studied metals.

Using the PBE0 functional supplemented with the D3(0) or, preferably, with higher class dispersion terms, used in our previous papers on gold as a cross-linking element and in other applications is a pragmatic, acceptable, but not particularly accurate approach.

When assessing the performance of DFT functionals, we pay attention to three classes of complexes. For closed-shell complexes of any size of the PEX chain with Be, Mg, and Zn atoms all functionals supplemented with implicit or explicit dispersion energy contribution exhibit BEs with absolute percentage errors of 11% or less with respect to DLPNO-CCSD(T) even though only CAM-B3LYP and PW6B95 perform with APE lower than 5%. Unfortunately, PW6B95 shows APE 20% or higher for some of PEX···PEX and PEX-Li-PEX complexes. Finding the overlap of well performing functionals for the closed-shell and doublet PEX-Li-PEX, PEX-Ag-

PEX, and PEX-Au-PEX complexes is even more difficult. Demanding is the selection of functionals for PEX-Li-PEX complexes. Errors of BEs lower than 6% with respect to DLPNO-CCSD(T1) shows only the ω B97X-D3 functional, followed by CAM-B3LYP with relatively high APE in the interval of 11 to 14%. Reasonable performance of several DFT functionals is found for PEX-Ag-PEX and PEX-Au-PEX complexes. Excluding Li complexes from the PEX-M-PEX set, six functionals have MAPE lower than 5%, namely CAM-B3LYP, ω B97X-D3, PW6B95, M06, TPSS0, B3LYP. Only slightly higher MAPE exhibit BEs with PBE0 and M06-L functionals, all supplemented with D3(BJ)-ABC except of ω B97X-D3, M06 and M06-L.

In search of DFT functionals for several cross-linking atoms in PEX-M-PEX complexes leading to BEs with similar accuracy, we suggest focusing to the most difficult case first (Li complexes in our CMC-D set) followed by searching the overlap with acceptable functionals for less problematic species afterwards.

Attention should be paid to the selection of reference BEs for benchmarking of DFT functionals for systems for which experimental data are missing. “Gold standard” of quantum chemistry, the single reference CCSD(T) method is a good choice. Using at least basic indicators of the non-dynamical correlation is a must. For larger systems, the DLPNO-CCSD(T) approximation is an excellent choice. For some cases, namely for complexes with Ag and Au, BEs with DLPNO-CCSD(T) differ from canonical CCSD(T) values significantly. A possible remedy is using the slightly more expensive iterative treatment of triples, i.e., the DLPNO-CCSD(T1) method which was applied for doublet state complexes in the present study

The size of the PEX chains matter when considering absolute values of BEs. The error increases with the size, but relative error of DFT results with respect to DLPNO-CCSD(T) or DLPNO-CCSD(T1) is less sensitive. Well performing functionals exhibit linear dependence of BEs on the system size.

DLPNO-CCSD(T) binding energies and BEs with each DFT functional converge to the CBS limit differently. Our benchmark data are based on the extrapolation of BEs to the CBS limit using def2-TZVPP and def2-QZVPP basis sets. Selection of functionals based on CBS extrapolated BEs is preferred, but initial estimates of the performance of individual functionals can be done already at the def2-TZVPP level

BEs for PEX-M-PEX complexes with different crosslinking metal atoms rise in the order of $\text{Li} < \text{Ag} < \text{Au} < \text{Mg} < \text{Zn} < \text{Be}$. The bonding characteristics, thermochemical data and properties of these complexes with extended PE oligomer chains will be analyzed in the separate paper. Further extension of this study would be considering the transition metals as cross-linking elements. To tackle problems with quasi-degeneracy, benchmarking should be performed with respect to BEs calculated with higher level Coupled Cluster single reference methods or multi-reference CC or other methods, like CASPT2. For available benchmarks with participation of transition metals we can learn from data in, e.g., Refs. ^{121,122} and benchmarks by Wilson et al. ¹²³ with respect to the Completely Renormalized CR-CCSD(T) method for the treatment of the multireference problem Ref. ¹²⁴. We are presently unable to apply such methods to sufficiently extended PEX-M-PEX complexes.

AUTHOR INFORMATION

Corresponding Author

*E-mail: urban1@uniba.sk Phone: +412 902 219 988

ORCID

Martin Blaško: 0000-0001-5070-7774 e-mail martin.blasko@tuni.sk

Lukáš F. Pašteka: 0000-0002-0617-0524 e-mail lukas.f.pasteka@uniba.sk

Miroslav Urban: 0000-0003-0379-6414 e-mail urban1@uniba.sk

Author Contributions

The manuscript was written through contributions of all authors. All authors have given approval to the final version of the manuscript. All authors contributed equally.

Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

Supporting Information Available:

Archive in Supporting Information: Geometries of PEX \cdots PEX and PEX-M-PEX complexes optimized with def2-TZVPP and def2-QZVPP basis sets are available as a file Bench-PEX-M-PEX-Archive_Geometries.zip

Supporting Information:

Figure S1 MAPE (%) of BEs 25 DFT functionals for PEX \cdots PEX (X = 4, 5, 7, 9) and cross-linked PEX-M-PEX (M = Li, Be, Mg, Zn, Ag, Au) complexes with different number of carbon atoms X in each chain, plotted for each M-atom separately.

Figure S2 MAPE (%) of BEs 25 DFT functionals cross-linked PEX-M-PEX (M = Li, Be, Mg, Zn, Ag, Au) complexes with different number of carbon atoms X (X = 3, 5, 7, 9) in each chain.

Figure S3 MAPE (%) of BEs 25 DFT functionals for PEX \cdots PEX (X = 4, 5, 7, 9) and cross-linked PEX-M-PEX (M = Li, Be, Mg, Zn, Ag, Au; X = 3, 5, 7, 9) complexes with different number of carbon atoms X in each chain.

Figure S4 Dependence of BEs (CBS limit) for PEX \cdots PEX (X = 4, 5, 7, 9) and crosslinked PEX-M-PEX (M = Li, Be, Mg, Zn, Ag, Au) complexes on the number of carbon atoms in the oligomer chains with CAM-B3LYP+D3(BJ)-ABC (A), ω B97X-D3 (B), and PBE0+D3(BJ)-ABC (C) functionals.

Figure S5 Dependence of BEs (kJ/mol) of PEX \cdots PEX (X = 4, 5, 7 and 9) and cross-linked PEX-M-PEX (M = Li, Be, Mg, Zn, Ag, Au) complexes on the number of carbon atoms in the oligomer chains using the DLPNO-CCSD(T) method with QRO orbitals.

Table S1. Dependence of BEs (kJ/mol) of non-cross-linked PEX \cdots PEX (X = 4, 5, 7, 9) complexes on the number of carbon atoms in oligomer chains using the DLPNO-CCSD(T) method.

Table S2, S3, and S4 . Dependence of BEs (kJ/mol) of cross-linked PEX-M-PEX complexes on the number of carbon atoms in oligomer chains. DLPNO-CCSD(T1) method used for PEX-M-PEX (M = Li, Ag, Au; X = 3, 5, 7, 9) complexes and DLPNO-CCSD(T) method for PEX-M-PEX (M = Be, Mg, Zn; X = 3, 5, 7, 9) complexes. Def2-TZVPP, def2-QZVPP basis sets and the CBS limit data.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreements No. 739566 (FunGlass) and 810701 (LAMatCU). We also thank for the support from the Slovak Research and Development Agency (grants APVV-20-098 and APVV-20-0127) and the Scientific Grant Agency of the Slovak Republic VEGA (1/0777/19). This work was supported in part through the Comenius University in Bratislava CLARA@UNIBA.SK high performance computing facilities, services and staff expertise of Centre for Information Technology. <https://uniba.sk/en/HPC-Clara>. Part of calculations were performed in the Computing Centre of the Slovak Academy of Sciences using the Slovak infrastructure for high-performance computing supported by the Research & Development Operational Programme (ERDF project ITMS 26230120002 and 26210120002).

Graphical Abstract

REFERENCES

- (1) Chodák, I. High Modulus Polyethylene Fibres : Preparation, Properties and Modification by Crosslinking. *Prog. Polym. Sci* **1998**, *23*, 1409–1442.
- (2) Chung, T. C. M. Expanding Polyethylene and Polypropylene Applications to High-Energy Areas by Applying Polyolefin-Bonded Antioxidants. *Macromolecules* **2019**, *52*, 5618–5637. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.macromol.9b00855>.
- (3) Mauri, M.; Peterson, A.; Senol, A.; Elamin, K.; Gitsas, A.; Hjertberg, T.; Matic, A.; Gkourmpis, T.; Prieto, O.; Müller, C. Byproduct-Free Curing of a Highly Insulating Polyethylene Copolymer Blend: An Alternative to Peroxide Crosslinking. *J. Mater. Chem. C* **2018**, *6*, 11292–11302. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C8TC04494E>.
- (4) Williamson, J. B.; Lewis, S. E.; Johnson, R. R.; Manning, I. M.; Leibfarth, F. A. C–H Functionalization of Commodity Polymers. *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2019**, *58*, 8654–8668. <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.201810970>.
- (5) Paajanen, A.; Vaari, J.; Verho, T. Crystallization of Cross-Linked Polyethylene by Molecular Dynamics Simulation. *Polymer* **2019**, *171*, 80–86. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymer.2019.03.040>.
- (6) Akbarian, D.; Hamed, H.; Damirchi, B.; Yilmaz, D. E.; Penrod, K.; Woodward, W. H. H.; Moore, J.; Lanagan, M. T.; van Duin, A. C. T. Atomistic-Scale Insights into the Crosslinking of Polyethylene Induced by Peroxides. *Polymer* **2019**, *183*, 121901. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymer.2019.121901>.
- (7) Fuhrer, R.; Athanassiou, E. K.; Luechinger, N. A.; Stark, W. J. Crosslinking Metal Nanoparticles into the Polymer Backbone of Hydrogels Enables Preparation of Soft, Magnetic Field-Driven Actuators with Muscle-Like Flexibility. *Small* **2009**, *5*, 383–388. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sml.200801091>.

- (8) Bossé, F.; Das, P.; Belfiore, L. A. Annealing Effects on the Solid State Properties of Transition-Metal Coordination Complexes and Networks Based on Diene Polymers with Palladium Chloride. *J. Polym. Sci. Part B Polym. Phys.* **1996**, *34*, 909–923. [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1099-0488\(19960415\)34:5<909::AID-POLB10>3.0.CO;2-F](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1099-0488(19960415)34:5<909::AID-POLB10>3.0.CO;2-F).
- (9) Rupar, P. A.; Cambridge, G.; Winnik, M. A.; Manners, I. Reversible Cross-Linking of Polyisoprene Coronas in Micelles, Block Comicelles, and Hierarchical Micelle Architectures Using Pt(0)–Olefin Coordination. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2011**, *133*, 16947–16957. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ja206370k>.
- (10) Eguchi, Y.; Kato, T.; Tanaka, T.; Maruyama, T. A DNA–Gold Nanoparticle Hybrid Hydrogel Network Prepared by Enzymatic Reaction. *Chem. Commun.* **2017**, *53*, 5802–5805. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C7CC02435E>.
- (11) Svorčík, V.; Kolská, Z.; Kvítek, O.; Siegel, J.; Rezníčková, A.; Rezanka, P.; Záruba, K. “Soft and Rigid” Dithiols and Au Nanoparticles Grafting on Plasma-Treated Polyethyleneterephthalate. *Nanoscale Res. Lett.* **2011**, *6*, 607. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1556-276X-6-607>.
- (12) Prakash, J.; Pivin, J. C.; Swart, H. C. Noble Metal Nanoparticles Embedding into Polymeric Materials: From Fundamentals to Applications. *Adv. Colloid Interface Sci.* **2015**, *226*, 187–202. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cis.2015.10.010>.
- (13) Blaško, M.; Mach, P.; Antušek, A.; Urban, M. DFT Modeling of Cross-Linked Polyethylene: Role of Gold Atoms and Dispersion Interactions. *J. Phys. Chem. A* **2018**, *122*, 1496–1503. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpca.7b12232>.
- (14) Blaško, M.; Mach, P.; Antušek, A.; Urban, M. Correction to “DFT Modeling of Cross-Linked Polyethylene: Role of Gold Atoms and Dispersion Interactions.” *J. Phys. Chem. A* **2018**, *122*, 4591–4592. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpca.8b03343>.
- (15) Zaleski-Ejgierd, P.; Pyykkö, P. Bonding Analysis for Sterically Uncongested Simple Au-carbon Complexes. *Can. J. Chem.* **2009**, *87*, 798–801. <https://doi.org/10.1139/V09-013>.
- (16) Barysz, M.; Pyykkö, P. Strong Chemical Bonds to Gold. High Level Correlated Relativistic Results for Diatomic AuBe⁺, AuC⁺, AuMg⁺, and AuSi⁺. *Chem. Phys. Lett.* **1998**, *285*, 398–403. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0009-2614\(98\)00025-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0009-2614(98)00025-6).
- (17) Blaško, M.; Rajský, T.; Urban, M. A Comparative DFT Study of Interactions of Au and Small Gold Clusters Au_n (n = 2–4) with CH₃S and CH₂ Radicals. *Chem. Phys. Lett.* **2017**, *671*, 84–91. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cplett.2017.01.019>.
- (18) Pyykkö, P.; Patzschke, M.; Suurpere, J. Calculated Structures of [Au=C=Au]₂⁺ and Related Systems. *Chem. Phys. Lett.* **2003**, *381*, 45–52. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cplett.2003.09.045>.
- (19) Aguirre, F.; Husband, J.; Thompson, C. J.; Metz, R. B. Gas-Phase Photodissociation of AuCH₂⁺: The Dissociation Threshold of Jet-Cooled and Rotationally Thermalized Ions. *Chem. Phys. Lett.* **2000**, *318*, 466–470. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0009-2614\(00\)00044-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0009-2614(00)00044-0).
- (20) Heinemann, C.; Hertwig, R. H.; Wesendrup, R.; Koch, W.; Schwarz, H. Relativistic Effects on Bonding in Cationic Transition-Metal-Carbene Complexes: A Density-Functional Study. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **1995**, *117*, 495–500. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ja00106a057>.
- (21) Li, F.-X.; Armentrout, P. B. Activation of Methane by Gold Cations: Guided Ion Beam and Theoretical Studies. *J. Chem. Phys.* **2006**, *125*, 133114. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.2220038>.
- (22) Hrusak, J. Relativistic Effects in the Metal-Carbon Bond. A Comparative Ab Initio and DFT Study of M=CH₂⁺ and M-CH₃⁺ (M=Cu, Ag and Au). *SOUTH Afr. J. Chem.-SUID-Afr. Tydskr. VIR Chem.* **1997**, *50*, 93–101.
- (23) Liu, H.-T.; Xiong, X.-G.; Diem Dau, P.; Wang, Y.-L.; Huang, D.-L.; Li, J.; Wang, L.-S. Probing the Nature of Gold–Carbon Bonding in Gold–Alkynyl Complexes. *Nat. Commun.* **2013**, *4*, 2223. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms3223>.
- (24) Tarakeshwar, P.; Buseck, P. R.; Kroto, H. W. Pseudocarbynes: Charge-Stabilized Carbon Chains. *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* **2016**, *7*, 1675–1681. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcllett.6b00671>.
- (25) León, I.; Ruipérez, F.; Ugalde, J. M.; Wang, L.-S. Probing the Electronic Structure and Au–C Chemical Bonding in AuC_n[–] and AuC_nH[–] (n = 2, 4, and 6) Using High-Resolution Photoelectron Spectroscopy. *J. Chem. Phys.* **2016**, *145*, 064304. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4960440>.

- (26) Antušek, A.; Blaško, M.; Urban, M.; Noga, P.; Kisić, D.; Nenadović, M.; Lončarević, D.; Rakočević, Z. Density Functional Theory Modeling of C–Au Chemical Bond Formation in Gold Implanted Polyethylene. *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **2017**, *19*, 28897–28906. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C7CP05637K>.
- (27) Iliáš, M.; Kellö, V.; Urban, M. Relativistic Effects in Atomic and Molecular Properties. *Acta Phys. Slovaca* **2010**, *60*, 259–391. <https://doi.org/10.2478/v10155-010-0003-1>.
- (28) Pyykkö, P. Relativistic Effects in Chemistry: More Common Than You Thought. *Annu. Rev. Phys. Chem.* **2012**, *63*, 45–64. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-physchem-032511-143755>.
- (29) Schwerdtfeger, P.; Smits, O. R.; Pyykkö, P. The Periodic Table and the Physics That Drives It. *Nat. Rev. Chem.* **2020**, *4*, 359–380. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41570-020-0195-y>.
- (30) Adamo, C.; Barone, V. Toward Reliable Density Functional Methods without Adjustable Parameters: The PBE0 Model. *J. Chem. Phys.* **1999**, *110*, 6158–6170. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.478522>.
- (31) Grimme, S.; Antony, J.; Ehrlich, S.; Krieg, H. A Consistent and Accurate Ab Initio Parametrization of Density Functional Dispersion Correction (DFT-D) for the 94 Elements H–Pu. *J. Chem. Phys.* **2010**, *132*, 154104. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.3382344>.
- (32) Pašteka, L. F.; Rajský, T.; Urban, M. Toward Understanding the Bonding Character in Complexes of Coinage Metals with Lone-Pair Ligands. CCSD(T) and DFT Computations. *J. Phys. Chem. A* **2013**, *117*, 4472–4485. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jp401174p>.
- (33) Rajský, T.; Urban, M. Au_n (n = 1,11) Clusters Interacting With Lone-Pair Ligands. *J. Phys. Chem. A* **2016**, *120*, 3938–3949. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpca.6b01235>.
- (34) Vícha, J.; Patzschke, M.; Marek, R. A Relativistic DFT Methodology for Calculating the Structures and NMR Chemical Shifts of Octahedral Platinum and Iridium Complexes. *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **2013**, *15*, 7740. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c3cp44440f>.
- (35) Minenkov, Y.; Chermak, E.; Cavallo, L. Troubles in the Systematic Prediction of Transition Metal Thermochemistry with Contemporary Out-of-the-Box Methods. *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* **2016**, *12*, 1542–1560. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jctc.5b01163>.
- (36) Yu, H. S.; He, X.; Truhlar, D. G. MN15-L: A New Local Exchange–Correlation Functional for Kohn–Sham Density Functional Theory with Broad Accuracy for Atoms, Molecules, and Solids. *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* **2016**, *12*, 1280–1293. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jctc.5b01082>.
- (37) Quintal, M. M.; Karton, A.; Iron, M. A.; Boese, A. D.; Martin, J. M. L. Benchmark Study of DFT Functionals for Late-Transition-Metal Reactions. *J. Phys. Chem. A* **2006**, *110*, 709–716. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jp054449w>.
- (38) Perdew, J. P.; Ruzsinszky, A.; Tao, J.; Staroverov, V. N.; Scuseria, G. E.; Csonka, G. I. Prescription for the Design and Selection of Density Functional Approximations: More Constraint Satisfaction with Fewer Fits. *J. Chem. Phys.* **2005**, *123*, 062201. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.1904565>.
- (39) Raghavachari, K.; Trucks, G. W.; Pople, J. A.; Head-Gordon, M. A Fifth-Order Perturbation Comparison of Electron Correlation Theories. *Chem. Phys. Lett.* **1989**, *157*, 479–483. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0009-2614\(89\)87395-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0009-2614(89)87395-6).
- (40) Urban, M.; Noga, J.; Cole, S. J.; Bartlett, R. J. Towards a Full CCSDT Model for Electron Correlation. *J. Chem. Phys.* **1985**, *83*, 4041–4046. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.449067>.
- (41) Mardirossian, N.; Head-Gordon, M. Thirty Years of Density Functional Theory in Computational Chemistry: An Overview and Extensive Assessment of 200 Density Functionals. *Mol. Phys.* **2017**, *115*, 2315–2372. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00268976.2017.1333644>.
- (42) Yu, H. S.; He, X.; Li, S. L.; Truhlar, D. G. MN15: A Kohn–Sham Global-Hybrid Exchange–Correlation Density Functional with Broad Accuracy for Multi-Reference and Single-Reference Systems and Noncovalent Interactions. *Chem. Sci.* **2016**, *7*, 5032–5051. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C6SC00705H>.
- (43) Cramer, C. J.; Truhlar, D. G. Density Functional Theory for Transition Metals and Transition Metal Chemistry. *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **2009**, *11*, 10757. <https://doi.org/10.1039/b907148b>.

- (44) Martin, J. M. L.; Santra, G. Empirical Double-Hybrid Density Functional Theory: A 'Third Way' in Between WFT and DFT. *Isr. J. Chem.* **2020**, *60*, 787-804. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ijch.201900114>.
- (45) Mollenhauer, D.; Gaston, N. A Balanced Procedure for the Treatment of Cluster-Ligand Interactions on Gold Phosphine Systems in Catalysis. *J. Comput. Chem.* **2014**, *35*, 986-997. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jcc.23578>.
- (46) Bernardi, F.; Bottoni, A.; Garavelli, M. Exploring Organic Chemistry with DFT: Radical, Organometallic, and Bio-organic Applications. *Quant. Struct.-Act. Relat* **2002**, *21*, 128-148. [https://doi.org/10.1002/1521-3838\(200207\)21:2<128::AID-QSAR128>3.0.CO;2-B](https://doi.org/10.1002/1521-3838(200207)21:2<128::AID-QSAR128>3.0.CO;2-B).
- (47) Nazarian, D.; Ganesh, P.; Sholl, D. S. Benchmarking Density Functional Theory Predictions of Framework Structures and Properties in a Chemically Diverse Test Set of Metal-Organic Frameworks. *J. Mater. Chem. A* **2015**, *3*, 22432-22440. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C5TA03864B>.
- (48) Chan, B.; Ball, G. E. A Benchmark Ab Initio and DFT Study of the Structure and Binding of Methane in the σ -Alkane Complex $\text{CpRe}(\text{CO})_2(\text{CH}_4)$. *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* **2013**, *9*, 2199-2208. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ct400013p>.
- (49) Rijs, N. J.; Brookes, N. J.; O'Hair, R. A. J.; Yates, B. F. Theoretical Approaches To Estimating Homolytic Bond Dissociation Energies of Organocopper and Organosilver Compounds. *J. Phys. Chem. A* **2012**, *116*, 8910-8917. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jp305718z>.
- (50) Minenkov, Y.; Chermak, E.; Cavallo, L. Accuracy of DLPNO-CCSD(T) Method for Noncovalent Bond Dissociation Enthalpies from Coinage Metal Cation Complexes. *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* **2015**, *11*, 4664-4676. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jctc.5b00584>.
- (51) Goerigk, L.; Hansen, A.; Bauer, C.; Ehrlich, S.; Najibi, A.; Grimme, S. A Look at the Density Functional Theory Zoo with the Advanced GMTKN55 Database for General Main Group Thermochemistry, Kinetics and Noncovalent Interactions. *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **2017**, *19*, 32184-32215. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C7CP04913G>.
- (52) Semidalas, E.; Martin, J. M. L. Canonical and DLPNO-Based G4(MP2)XK-Inspired Composite Wave Function Methods Parametrized against Large and Chemically Diverse Training Sets: Are They More Accurate and/or Robust than Double-Hybrid DFT? *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* **2020**, *16*, 4238-4255. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jctc.0c00189>.
- (53) Bursch, M.; Caldeweyher, E.; Hansen, A.; Neugebauer, H.; Ehlert, S.; Grimme, S. Understanding and Quantifying London Dispersion Effects in Organometallic Complexes. *Acc. Chem. Res.* **2019**, *52*, 258-266. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.accounts.8b00505>.
- (54) Liu, C.-S.; Pilania, G.; Wang, C.; Ramprasad, R. How Critical Are the van Der Waals Interactions in Polymer Crystals? *J. Phys. Chem. A* **2012**, *116*, 9347-9352. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jp3005844>.
- (55) Lu, Q.; Neese, F.; Bistoni, G. London Dispersion Effects in the Coordination and Activation of Alkanes in σ -Complexes: A Local Energy Decomposition Study. *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **2019**, *21*, 11569-11577. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C9CP01309A>.
- (56) Modrzejewski, M.; Hapka, M.; Chalasinski, G.; Szczesniak, M. M. Employing Range Separation on the Meta-GGA Rung: New Functional Suitable for Both Covalent and Noncovalent Interactions. *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* **2016**, *12*, 3662-3673. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jctc.6b00406>.
- (57) Tunega, D.; Bučko, T.; Zaoui, A. Assessment of Ten DFT Methods in Predicting Structures of Sheet Silicates: Importance of Dispersion Corrections. *J. Chem. Phys.* **2012**, *137*, 114105. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4752196>.
- (58) Burns, L. A.; Mayagoitia, Á. V.-; Sumpter, B. G.; Sherrill, C. D. Density-Functional Approaches to Noncovalent Interactions: A Comparison of Dispersion Corrections (DFT-D), Exchange-Hole Dipole Moment (XDM) Theory, and Specialized Functionals. *J. Chem. Phys.* **2011**, *134*, 084107. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.3545971>.
- (59) Goerigk, L.; Kruse, H.; Grimme, S. Benchmarking Density Functional Methods against the S66 and S66x8 Datasets for Non-Covalent Interactions. *ChemPhysChem* **2011**, *12*, 3421-3433. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cphc.201100826>.

- (60) Řezáč, J.; Riley, K. E.; Hobza, P. S66: A Well-Balanced Database of Benchmark Interaction Energies Relevant to Biomolecular Structures. *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* **2011**, *7*, 2427–2438. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ct2002946>.
- (61) Gráfová, L.; Pitoňák, M.; Řezáč, J.; Hobza, P. Comparative Study of Selected Wave Function and Density Functional Methods for Noncovalent Interaction Energy Calculations Using the Extended S22 Data Set. *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* **2010**, *6*, 2365–2376. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ct1002253>.
- (62) Klimeš, J.; Michaelides, A. Perspective: Advances and Challenges in Treating van Der Waals Dispersion Forces in Density Functional Theory. *J. Chem. Phys.* **2012**, *137*, 120901. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4754130>.
- (63) Osuna, S.; Swart, M.; Solà, M. Dispersion Corrections Essential for the Study of Chemical Reactivity in Fullerenes. *J. Phys. Chem. A* **2011**, *115*, 3491–3496. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jp1091575>.
- (64) Řezáč, J.; Hobza, P. Benchmark Calculations of Interaction Energies in Noncovalent Complexes and Their Applications. *Chem. Rev.* **2016**, *116*, 5038–5071. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemrev.5b00526>.
- (65) Giraudo, M.; Schuy, C.; Weber, U.; Rovituro, M.; Santin, G.; Norbury, J. W.; Tracino, E.; Menicucci, A.; Bocchini, L.; Lobascio, C. et al. Accelerator-Based Tests of Shielding Effectiveness of Different Materials and Multilayers Using High-Energy Light and Heavy Ions. *Radiat. Res.* **2018**, *190*, 526–537. <https://doi.org/10.1667/RR15111.1>.
- (66) Müller, J. Nucleic Acid Duplexes with Metal-Mediated Base Pairs and Their Structures. *Coord. Chem. Rev.* **2019**, *393*, 37–47. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ccr.2019.05.007>.
- (67) Ivanov, A. S.; Kar, T.; Boldyrev, A. I. Nanoscale Stabilization of Zintl Compounds: 1D Ionic Li–P Double Helix Confined inside a Carbon Nanotube. *Nanoscale* **2016**, *8*, 3454–3460. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C5NR07713C>.
- (68) Riplinger, C.; Sandhoefer, B.; Hansen, A.; Neese, F. Natural Triple Excitations in Local Coupled Cluster Calculations with Pair Natural Orbitals. *J. Chem. Phys.* **2013**, *139*, 134101. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4821834>.
- (69) Liakos, D. G.; Guo, Y.; Neese, F. Comprehensive Benchmark Results for the Domain Based Local Pair Natural Orbital Coupled Cluster Method (DLPNO-CCSD(T)) for Closed- and Open-Shell Systems. *J. Phys. Chem. A* **2020**, *124*, 90–100. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpca.9b05734>.
- (70) Schütz, M.; Werner, H.-J. Local Perturbative Triples Correction (T) with Linear Cost Scaling. *Chem. Phys. Lett.* **2000**, *318*, 370–378. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0009-2614\(00\)00066-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0009-2614(00)00066-X).
- (71) Nagy, P. R.; Kállay, M. Approaching the Basis Set Limit of CCSD(T) Energies for Large Molecules with Local Natural Orbital Coupled-Cluster Methods. *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* **2019**, *15*, 5275–5298. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jctc.9b00511>.
- (72) Sylvetsky, N.; Banerjee, A.; Alonso, M.; Martin, J. M. L. Performance of Localized Coupled Cluster Methods in a Moderately Strong Correlation Regime: Hückel–Möbius Interconversions in Expanded Porphyrins. *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* **2020**, *16*, 3641–3653. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jctc.0c00297>.
- (73) Grimme, S.; Ehrlich, S.; Goerigk, L. Effect of the Damping Function in Dispersion Corrected Density Functional Theory. *J. Comput. Chem.* **2011**, *32*, 1456–1465. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jcc.21759>.
- (74) Proynov, E.; Liu, F.; Gan, Z.; Wang, M.; Kong, J. Density-Functional Approach to the Three-Body Dispersion Interaction Based on the Exchange Dipole Moment. *J. Chem. Phys.* **2015**, *143*, 084125. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4929581>.
- (75) Neese, F. The ORCA Program System: The ORCA Program System. *Wiley Interdiscip. Rev. Comput. Mol. Sci.* **2012**, *2*, 73–78. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wcms.81>.
- (76) Neese, F. Software Update: The ORCA Program System, Version 4.0. *WIREs Comput. Mol. Sci.* **2018**, *8*, e1327. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wcms.1327>.

- (77) Grimme, S. Accurate Description of van Der Waals Complexes by Density Functional Theory Including Empirical Corrections. *J. Comput. Chem.* **2004**, *25*, 1463–1473. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jcc.20078>.
- (78) Grimme, S. Semiempirical GGA-Type Density Functional Constructed with a Long-Range Dispersion Correction. *J. Comput. Chem.* **2006**, *27*, 1787–1799. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jcc.20495>.
- (79) Yanai, T.; Tew, D. P.; Handy, N. C. A New Hybrid Exchange–Correlation Functional Using the Coulomb-Attenuating Method (CAM-B3LYP). *Chem. Phys. Lett.* **2004**, *393*, 51–57. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cplett.2004.06.011>.
- (80) Weigend, F.; Ahlrichs, R. Balanced Basis Sets of Split Valence, Triple Zeta Valence and Quadruple Zeta Valence Quality for H to Rn: Design and Assessment of Accuracy. *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **2005**, *7*, 3297. <https://doi.org/10.1039/b508541a>.
- (81) Boys, S. F.; Bernardi, F. The Calculation of Small Molecular Interactions by the Differences of Separate Total Energies. Some Procedures with Reduced Errors. *Mol. Phys.* **1970**, *19*, 553–566. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00268977000101561>.
- (82) Riplinger, C.; Pinski, P.; Becker, U.; Valeev, E. F.; Neese, F. Sparse Maps—A Systematic Infrastructure for Reduced-Scaling Electronic Structure Methods. II. Linear Scaling Domain Based Pair Natural Orbital Coupled Cluster Theory. *J. Chem. Phys.* **2016**, *144*, 024109. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4939030>.
- (83) Neese, F.; Solomon, E. I. Calculation of Zero-Field Splittings, g-Values, and the Relativistic Nephelauxetic Effect in Transition Metal Complexes. Application to High-Spin Ferric Complexes †. *Inorg. Chem.* **1998**, *37*, 6568–6582. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ic980948i>.
- (84) Neese, F. Importance of Direct Spin–Spin Coupling and Spin-Flip Excitations for the Zero-Field Splittings of Transition Metal Complexes: A Case Study. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2006**, *128*, 10213–10222. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ja061798a>.
- (85) Liakos, D. G.; Sparta, M.; Kesharwani, M. K.; Martin, J. M. L.; Neese, F. Exploring the Accuracy Limits of Local Pair Natural Orbital Coupled-Cluster Theory. *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* **2015**, *11*, 1525–1539. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ct501129s>.
- (86) Guo, Y.; Riplinger, C.; Becker, U.; Liakos, D. G.; Minenkov, Y.; Cavallo, L.; Neese, F. Communication: An Improved Linear Scaling Perturbative Triples Correction for the Domain Based Local Pair-Natural Orbital Based Singles and Doubles Coupled Cluster Method [DLPNO-CCSD(T)]. *J. Chem. Phys.* **2018**, *148*, 011101. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.5011798>.
- (87) Halkier, A.; Helgaker, T.; Jørgensen, P.; Klopper, W.; Koch, H.; Olsen, J.; Wilson, A. K. Basis-Set Convergence in Correlated Calculations on Ne, N₂, and H₂O. *Chem. Phys. Lett.* **1998**, *286*, 243–252. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0009-2614\(98\)00111-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0009-2614(98)00111-0).
- (88) Anatole von Lilienfeld, O.; Tkatchenko, A. Two- and Three-Body Interatomic Dispersion Energy Contributions to Binding in Molecules and Solids. *J. Chem. Phys.* **2010**, *132*, 234109. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.3432765>.
- (89) Haaland, A.; Green, J. C.; McGrady, G. S.; Downs, A. J.; Gullo, E.; Lyall, M. J.; Timberlake, J.; Tutukin, A. V.; Volden, H. V.; Østby, K.-A. The Length, Strength and Polarity of Metal–Carbon Bonds: Dialkylzinc Compounds Studied by Density Functional Theory Calculations, Gas Electron Diffraction and Photoelectron Spectroscopy. *Dalton Trans* **2003**, No. 22, 4356–4366. <https://doi.org/10.1039/B306840B>.
- (90) Lee, T. J. Comparison of the T1 and D1 Diagnostics for Electronic Structure Theory: A New Definition for the Open-Shell D1 Diagnostic. *Chem. Phys. Lett.* **2003**, *372*, 362–367. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0009-2614\(03\)00435-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0009-2614(03)00435-4).
- (91) Martin, J. M. L. The Eight-Valence-Electron Systems Re-Examined: Convergence of the Coupled-Cluster Series and Performance of Quasiperturbative Methods for Quadruple Excitations. *Mol. Phys.* **2014**, *112*, 785–793. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00268976.2013.861526>.
- (92) Watts, J. D.; Urban, M.; Bartlett, R. J. Accurate Electrical and Spectroscopic Properties Of X¹⁺ BeO from Coupled-Cluster Methods. *Theor. Chim. Acta* **1995**, *90*, 341–355. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01113541>.

- (93) Bartlett, R. J.; Park, Y. C.; Bauman, N. P.; Melnichuk, A.; Ranasinghe, D.; Ravi, M.; Perera, A. Index of Multi-Determinantal and Multi-Reference Character in Coupled-Cluster Theory. *J. Chem. Phys.* **2020**, *153*, 234103. <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0029339>.
- (94) Fogueri, U. R.; Kozuch, S.; Karton, A.; Martin, J. M. L. A Simple DFT-Based Diagnostic for Nondynamical Correlation. *Theor. Chem. Acc.* **2013**, *132*, 1291. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00214-012-1291-y>.
- (95) Sandler, I.; Chen, J.; Taylor, M.; Sharma, S.; Ho, J. Accuracy of DLPNO-CCSD(T): Effect of Basis Set and System Size. *J. Phys. Chem. A* **2021**, *125*, 1553–1563. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpca.0c11270>.
- (96) Lee, C.; Yang, W.; Parr, R. G. Development of the Colle-Salvetti Correlation-Energy Formula into a Functional of the Electron Density. *Phys. Rev. B* **1988**, *37*, 785–789. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.37.785>.
- (97) Miehlich, B.; Savin, A.; Stoll, H.; Preuss, H. Results Obtained with the Correlation Energy Density Functionals of Becke and Lee, Yang and Parr. *Chem. Phys. Lett.* **1989**, *157*, 200–206. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0009-2614\(89\)87234-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0009-2614(89)87234-3).
- (98) Handy, N. C.; Cohen, A. J. Left-Right Correlation Energy. *Mol. Phys.* **2001**, *99*, 403–412. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00268970010018431>.
- (99) Staroverov, V. N.; Scuseria, G. E.; Tao, J.; Perdew, J. P. Comparative Assessment of a New Nonempirical Density Functional: Molecules and Hydrogen-Bonded Complexes. *J. Chem. Phys.* **2003**, *119*, 12129–12137. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.1626543>.
- (100) Sun, J.; Ruzsinszky, A.; Perdew, J. P. Strongly Constrained and Appropriately Normed Semilocal Density Functional. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **2015**, *115*, 036402. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.115.036402>.
- (101) Becke, A. D. A New Mixing of Hartree–Fock and Local Density-functional Theories. *J. Chem. Phys.* **1993**, *98*, 1372–1377. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.464304>.
- (102) Grimme, S. Semiempirical Hybrid Density Functional with Perturbative Second-Order Correlation. *J. Chem. Phys.* **2006**, *124*, 034108. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.2148954>.
- (103) Tao, J.; Perdew, J.; Staroverov, V.; Scuseria, G. Climbing the Density Functional Ladder: Nonempirical Meta–Generalized Gradient Approximation Designed for Molecules and Solids. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **2003**, *91*, 146401. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.91.146401>.
- (104) Zhao, Y.; Truhlar, D. G. The M06 Suite of Density Functionals for Main Group Thermochemistry, Thermochemical Kinetics, Noncovalent Interactions, Excited States, and Transition Elements: Two New Functionals and Systematic Testing of Four M06-Class Functionals and 12 Other Functionals. *Theor. Chem. Acc.* **2008**, *120*, 215–241. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00214-007-0310-x>.
- (105) Zhao, Y.; Truhlar, D. G. The M06 Suite of Density Functionals for Main Group Thermochemistry, Thermochemical Kinetics, Noncovalent Interactions, Excited States, and Transition Elements: Two New Functionals and Systematic Testing of Four M06 Functionals and 12 Other Functionals. *Theor. Chem. Acc.* **2008**, *119*, 525–525. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00214-007-0401-8>.
- (106) Zhao, Y.; Truhlar, D. G. A New Local Density Functional for Main-Group Thermochemistry, Transition Metal Bonding, Thermochemical Kinetics, and Noncovalent Interactions. *J. Chem. Phys.* **2006**, *125*, 194101. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.2370993>.
- (107) Ramos-Berdullas, N.; Pérez-Juste, I.; Van Alsenoy, C.; Mandado, M. Theoretical Study of the Adsorption of Aromatic Units on Carbon Allotropes Including Explicit (Empirical) DFT Dispersion Corrections and Implicitly Dispersion-Corrected Functionals: The Pyridine Case. *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **2015**, *17*, 575–587. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C4CP02341B>.
- (108) Lin, Y.-S.; Li, G.-D.; Mao, S.-P.; Chai, J.-D. Long-Range Corrected Hybrid Density Functionals with Improved Dispersion Corrections. *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* **2013**, *9*, 263–272. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ct300715s>.

- (109) Chai, J.-D.; Head-Gordon, M. Long-Range Corrected Hybrid Density Functionals with Damped Atom–Atom Dispersion Corrections. *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **2008**, *10*, 6615. <https://doi.org/10.1039/b810189b>.
- (110) Najibi, A.; Goerigk, L. The Nonlocal Kernel in van Der Waals Density Functionals as an Additive Correction: An Extensive Analysis with Special Emphasis on the B97M-V and Ω B97M-V Approaches. *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* **2018**, *14*, 5725–5738. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jctc.8b00842>.
- (111) Riley, K. E.; Pitoňák, M.; Jurečka, P.; Hobza, P. Stabilization and Structure Calculations for Noncovalent Interactions in Extended Molecular Systems Based on Wave Function and Density Functional Theories. *Chem. Rev.* **2010**, *110*, 5023–5063. <https://doi.org/10.1021/cr1000173>.
- (112) Zhao, Y.; Truhlar, D. G. Design of Density Functionals That Are Broadly Accurate for Thermochemistry, Thermochemical Kinetics, and Nonbonded Interactions. *J. Phys. Chem. A* **2005**, *109*, 5656–5667. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jp050536c>.
- (113) Becke, A. D. Density-functional Thermochemistry. III. The Role of Exact Exchange. *J. Chem. Phys.* **1993**, *98*, 5648–5652. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.464913>.
- (114) Perdew, J. P.; Yue, W. Accurate and Simple Density Functional for the Electronic Exchange Energy: Generalized Gradient Approximation. *Phys. Rev. B* **1986**, *33*, 8800–8802. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.33.8800>.
- (115) Perdew, J. P.; Yue, W. Erratum: Accurate and Simple Density Functional for the Electronic Exchange Energy: Generalized Gradient Approximation. *Phys. Rev. B* **1989**, *40*, 3399–3399. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.40.3399>.
- (116) Bickelhaupt, F. M.; Solà, M.; Guerra, C. F. Highly Polar Bonds and the Meaning of Covalency and Ionicity—Structure and Bonding of Alkali Metal Hydride Oligomers. *Faraday Discuss* **2007**, *135*, 451–468. <https://doi.org/10.1039/B606093E>.
- (117) Wheeler, S. E.; Sattelmeyer, K. W.; Schleyer, P. v. R.; Schaefer, H. F. Binding Energies of Small Lithium Clusters (Lin) and Hydrogenated Lithium Clusters (LinH). *J. Chem. Phys.* **2004**, *120*, 4683–4689. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.1645242>.
- (118) Hait, D.; Liang, Y. H.; Head-Gordon, M. Too Big, Too Small, or Just Right? A Benchmark Assessment of Density Functional Theory for Predicting the Spatial Extent of the Electron Density of Small Chemical Systems. *J. Chem. Phys.* **2021**, *154*, 074109. <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0038694>.
- (119) Grimme, S. Accurate Calculation of the Heats of Formation for Large Main Group Compounds with Spin-Component Scaled MP2 Methods. *J. Phys. Chem. A* **2005**, *109*, 3067–3077. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jp050036j>.
- (120) He, Q.; Liao, X.; Xia, L.; Li, Z.; Wang, H.; Zhao, Y.; Truhlar, D. G. Accurate Binding Energies for Lithium Polysulfides and Assessment of Density Functionals for Lithium–Sulfur Battery Research. *J. Phys. Chem. C* **2019**, *123*, 20737–20747. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcc.9b05235>.
- (121) Verma, P.; Varga, Z.; Klein, J. E. M. N.; Cramer, C. J.; Que, L.; Truhlar, D. G. Assessment of Electronic Structure Methods for the Determination of the Ground Spin States of Fe(II), Fe(III) and Fe(IV) Complexes. *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **2017**, *19*, 13049–13069. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C7CP01263B>.
- (122) Verma, P.; Truhlar, D. G. Can Kohn–Sham Density Functional Theory Predict Accurate Charge Distributions for Both Single-Reference and Multi-Reference Molecules? *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **2017**, *19*, 12898–12912. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C7CP01576C>.
- (123) Wang, J.; Liu, L.; Wilson, A. K. Oxidative Cleavage of the β -O-4 Linkage of Lignin by Transition Metals: Catalytic Properties and the Performance of Density Functionals. *J. Phys. Chem. A* **2016**, *120*, 737–746. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpca.5b08854>.
- (124) Kowalski, K.; Piecuch, P. The Method of Moments of Coupled-Cluster Equations and the Renormalized CCSD[T], CCSD(T), CCSD(TQ), and CCSDT(Q) Approaches. *J. Chem. Phys.* **2000**, *113*, 18–35. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.481769>.

